

PSYCHOLOGICAL MECHANISMS OF THE MODEL OF DEVELOPMENT OF REFLEXIVE ABILITIES IN STUDENTS

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Abstract. *This article describes the level of development of reflection, reflexive abilities and its role in personal development. Manifestation of reflexive abilities has an important place in the student's professional formation. As a reflection, a concept that requires philosophical understanding is illuminated, and the activity of self-awareness, which describes the form of human theoretical activity, reveals the spiritual world of a person, aimed at understanding one's own culture and its foundations, behaviors, is interpreted.*

Keywords: *reflection, student, ability, personality, self-management, autoreflection, socioreflection.*

Reflective processes are one of the most important characteristics of behavior and behavior that determine the effect of individual development and interpersonal relations. Among modern practical psychological service technologies, you can find various methods aimed at the goal of correction and development. Among them, currently the most common form of practical group psychological work is training sessions. Training as one of the special forms of education, based on continuous experiences, traditionally imparting knowledge covers the process of understanding the experience of interpersonal interaction, which is different from psychological counseling and psychotherapy. Sometimes the expression "experimental education" is used to clarify the meaning of this term. In the educational process of this form, the participants are not limited to thinking about reality and thinking about "what to do with it", but continuously understand its essence. An individual approach is important in the development of reflexive abilities in students. It is appropriate to use the ideas of cognitive therapy, humanistic orientation, person-oriented therapy, Gestalt therapy manifestations as a methodological basis for the manifestation of reflexive abilities in students, cognitive activity, approach as a value, sense of independence, tolerant attitude towards information.

Cognitive psychotherapy is a psychotherapeutic method aimed at changing a person's psychological problems and irrational or inappropriate thoughts and beliefs, as well as dysfunctional stereotypes of his thinking and perception [2].

The cognitive method of psychotherapy is a type of strategy for influencing the internal "I" signs and behavioral reactions of a person, which also affects his cognitive abilities. The use of cognitive psychotherapy requires a lot of work from the specialist, but as a result of its application, success is almost always achieved[3].

Recently, the work of cognitive psychotherapists has attracted the attention of the whole world. Cognitive psychotherapy centers were established in the United States and Europe. Psychologist Smith concluded that "the cognitive-behavioral approach is one of the most powerful, if not the strongest, today." Interest in cognitive approaches among psychotherapists has increased by 60% since 1973 [4]. Much of the research, theoretical development, and psychic training in cognitive psychotherapy has taken place at the Center for Cognitive Psychotherapy at the University of Pennsylvania or at centers established by those trained at the center.

Cognitive-behavioral psychotherapy is one of the directions based on the psychotherapeutic approach aimed at changing self-evaluation skills, strategies and directions in order to overcome problems related to human behavior and thinking. This trend was founded by the American psychotherapist Aaron Beck. Cognitive-behavioral psychotherapy was created on the basis of cognitive psychotherapy (cognitive therapy, 1967). Cognitive-behavioral psychotherapy is formed on the basis of two different schools, that is, behavioral and cognitive psychotherapy[4]:

Cognitive-behavioral psychotherapy is distinguished in the following three ways:

1. Cognition - consists of concepts such as recalling information, processing in the mind, reasoning and understanding.
 2. Conation consists of such concepts as goal-directed movement, motivation, instinct, desire and will.
 3. Affect - consists of emotional reactions and mood.
- Cognitive-behavioral psychotherapy seeks to solve the following goals and tasks:
1. Finding the cause of cognitive errors and behavioral disorders.
 2. Correction of pathological thoughts and behavior disorders caused by them.
 3. Prevention of relapse.
 4. Finding a solution to socio-psychological problems.

The famous American psychologist Aaron Beck, the founder of cognitive psychotherapy, combined in his method the ideas of psychoanalysis about the influence of the unconscious on our thoughts and actions, and the possibility of teaching a new type of human reactions to external events of behaviorists. Aron Beck believed that psychological problems arise from the fact that we make false conclusions that can seriously distort the facts.

In addition, each of us not only perceives and evaluates the situation. Maybe we constantly think about what he is thinking and feeling. Aron Beck called such comments "automatic thoughts" and believed that they can be the source of our experiences and inappropriate behavior. All passions and painful feelings arise from wrong conclusions. We make cause-and-effect relationships, but they are a game of our minds, so they can be wrong. Aron Beck said that this world is not bad, but that's how we see it. Today, Aron Beck's cognitive therapy is one of the main methods of the cognitive-behavioral approach in psychotherapy, which is effective in working with many psychological problems.

The study of psychological literature allows us to conclude that there are many different psychological mechanisms that ensure the development of this or that phenomenon. In addition, within the framework of certain studies, special emphasis is placed on the mechanism of regulation of the will (Lange N.N), reflexivity mechanisms in volitional activity (Artyukhova T.Yu., Mirziev I.Kh., Savinkina). Based on the specific characteristics of psychological mechanisms, we identified the physiological mechanism, relaxation mechanism, reflexive, motivational and volitional mechanisms that effectively contribute to the formation of self-control in students. (See Figure 1)

Figure 1. A model for the development of reflection in students

In this model, the main, generalized task is performed by the reflexive mechanism, because on the basis of its functions, the qualities of emotional stability in students are optimized.

And the function of the physiological mechanism can be determined by leading psychological motivations. This motivational system serves to ensure active adaptation to external conditions as a whole.

By the physiological factors of mental state control, we understand the readiness mechanism that ensures the adjustment of the organism and all its systems (respiratory, cardiovascular, muscular, endocrine, etc.) for future activities related to changing mental states.

Therefore, the physiological level of the structure of reflexive abilities of students, including neurophysiological characteristics, morphological and biochemical changes, the ability to adequately predict further actions and behaviors based on a comprehensive analysis of the specific conditions of life that affect the formation of physiological functions can be expressed as

Volitional qualities are a specific aspect of volitional control that is manifested in specific situations related to character, formed when overcoming difficulties, and become personal characteristics.

It should be noted that the manifestation of voluntary qualities is not only related to human motives, but also to his values, beliefs, and innate characteristics manifested in the nervous system. This relationship is especially evident in people whose nervous system is weak and inhibition is more important than excitability. For this reason, it is more difficult for them to act boldly.

Voluntary qualities are classified differently by a number of scientists in the literature where this problem is studied. For example, F. N. Gonobolin divides volitional qualities into two groups in connection with the excitability and inhibition of involuntary actions and mental processes: group 1 includes determination, courage, tenacity and independence; Group 2 includes patience, self-control, endurance, discipline and organization.

Relaxation is the psychophysiological mechanism that influences the mental state of the next students.

Relaxation (lat. *relaxatio* — weakening) is the process of returning a macroscopic system to its previous state after being removed from the state of thermodynamic equilibrium. The transition of the system to the equilibrium state occurs at a certain speed, and this speed depends not only on thermodynamic criteria (pressure, volume, etc.), but also on the microscopic

characteristics of the system, in particular, on the interactions of the particles that make up the system. The interaction largely depends on the path of free movement of particles and the time of free movement.

The development of reflexive abilities in students is an important aspect of personality, which allows a person to control his behavior. A person who has adequate self-control has such characteristics as subjugating his feelings to reason and making clear decisions in various situations. In addition, through reflexive abilities, the subject controls his emotional state. The predominance of the following characteristics in students based on the studied scientific sources served as the basis for the creation of the psychocorrective program of our study:

- individuality in acquiring knowledge, skills and qualifications;
- manifestation of individual style in activity;
- priority of professional motivation;
- strict leadership of spiritual need, stable interest;
- social-psychological relations are subject to personal position;
- expression of the higher education environment in the personality of the student;
- socio-psychological factors of adaptation to practice and environment.

Through these characteristics of students, we conducted psychocorrective work on the basis of the obtained preliminary empirical data.

In the framework of psychological research, the model of the process of developing reflexivity and reflexive position is especially distinguished. In this model, attention is paid to normative reflexive directions with complement (where the "forced" principle is implemented). After that, the process of comparing them with their desires and aspirations is carried out (this is the "I want" principle). Then the subject has a need to interpret social and professional rules personally. The desire for a personal interpretation of what is happening is related to the awareness of the basic possibilities of reflexive abilities (the principle of "I am able"), information at this level is consistent with the existing level of reflexive competence of the subject ("I have the principle").

The problem of developing reflection in psychology is, on the one hand, the formation of consciousness and self-awareness (S.L. Rubinstein, I.I. Chesnokova, N.I. Chuprikova, L.I. Bojovich, V.I. Slobodchikov, G.V. Akopov, M.E. Manshin, Ye.I. Isaev), personal reflection (N.I. Gutkina), related to the problems of intellectual reflection (in collaboration with I.N. Semenov, S.Yu. Stepanov, as well as M.I. Naydenova, G.F. Pokhmelkina, N.B. Kovaleva, A.V. Sovetov, I.V. Palaginalar), on the other hand, researching the problems of theoretical thinking (L.S. Vygotsky, V.V. Davidov) and the study of practical thinking issues (Y.N. Kulyutkin, G.S. Sukhobskaya), and can also be considered from the point of view of the formation of a creative personality (V.G. Bogin). It should be noted that most of the studies on the development of reflection are aimed at forming reflection as a mental process.

All methods of developing reflexivity can be conditionally divided into two main large groups. The first group of methods includes a person's worldview and psychological assumptions; the very environment in which education is carried out; methods aimed at changing the "ideology" underlying all processes of education are introduced. In order to start the process of reflection, the student should be placed in such a situation that the manifestation of reflexivity, that is, the movement aimed at turning to one's inner world, one's own experience, is supported by any means. The meaning of showing a reflexive position is as follows: the student refuses to use the usual

methods in his activity or thinking, stops actions, i.e. practical activity, thinking, communication. In this case, he "goes to the edge", one can say, he turns away from the "environment" of this activity and begins to look at it from the surface, turns it into an object of observation, begins to "see" it anew (and sometimes for the first time can reach) and proceeds to analysis.

The process of reflection begins with the first moments of the awareness of "not knowing" and the emergence of "knowing about not knowing". A person does not have the need to learn or understand something without "knowing that he does not know". The first group of reflective teaching methods includes methods that are designed to create conditions when necessary. The second group includes didactic methods. These methods are aimed at bringing the teenager and student to reflection, reflexive position and activating it. However, it is difficult to establish a clear boundary between these two groups [1].

Undoubtedly, the development of reflexivity as an attribute implies the development of the individual. The development of reflexivity should be carried out in two directions, that is, in the development of intrapsychic reflexivity and interpsychic reflexivity. Intrapsychic reflexivity refers to adequate self-assessment, self-perception, self-acceptance, etc. Interpsychic reflexivity is the ability to "stand in the place of another", that is, social reflexivity. Therefore, the development of intrapsychic reflexivity implies the development of internal reflexivity, and the development of interpsychic reflexivity implies the development of external reflexivity. The training sessions used in the formative part of the study are aimed at developing reflexive abilities, emotional state management and self-control processes in emotional states, as well as personality traits. After the completion of the training sessions, the psychodiagnostic examination was conducted again with the test students using appropriate methods and the results were analyzed.

Thus, by considering the problem of developing reflexivity in a person, it is necessary to accept it as an integrative reality. This reality appears at the same time as a mental process, a state, but it does not belong to any of them. This is the ability in which a person imagines himself and separates his "I" from the environment, as a result, he can create his own worldview, turn his subjectivity into a subject of awareness, understand, and most importantly, it can be processed in practice. can see as an object. As a mental property, reflexivity is manifested as a subject property and has its own individual dimension.

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